

Original Research Article

Effects of Marketing Mix Elements on Customer's Patronage and Loyalty (A Study of Five Domino Pizza Outlets on the Mainland, Lagos, Nigeria)

Abimbade A. Babawale¹, Dr. Ebiere Kolawole^{1*}, Moses C. Ekperiware¹, John A. Oyetade², Adeyinka Adewusi¹

Abstract

¹Caleb University, Lagos State, Nigeria

²Lagos State University of Science and Technology, Ikorodu, Lagos State, Nigeria)

*Corresponding Author's E-mail: moses.ekperiware@calebuniversity.edu.ng

Competition in the markets is getting stiffer as the working environment is constantly changing in intricacies. A variety of companies seem to have that their customers are seeking better products and value from competing brands to obtain satisfaction, and more value for their money. Hyun (2010) opined that the issue of customer's patronage and loyalty came to the fore when marketers realize that many disgruntled customers do not essentially return to purchase their services and products and which afterwards affects revenue generated from sales. This study investigates the effects of marketing mix on customer's patronage in Domino Pizza, Lagos. The descriptive research was adopted using descriptive survey method. Questionnaire was used to collect data which was processed using SPSS. A total of Three hundred questionnaires (300) copies of questionnaires were distributed among the customers of Domino Pizza, of which only one hundred and twenty (120) questionnaires were completed and returned. The hypotheses were tested using both correlations and regression investigations. The findings opined that marketing mix has the highest tendency to affect customers' patronage. This is evident because the effective combination of the marketing mix elements can drive the organization towards their objective and improve their performance in term of short term and long-term performance of the company to improve customer's patronage and loyalty. If customer's patronage is low, there will be decrease in the profit level, low productivity, wastages in resources and other factors that can bring up loss to the company. It should be recommended that; new techniques and methods in connection with marketing mix should be adopted to ensure continued customers' patronage and loyalty to Domino Pizza; Favourable pricing should be employed in Domino Pizza and channeled to boosting customers' patronage and loyalty, The customers should be given high and friendly treatments in the organization to ensure more patronages

Keywords: Efficiency, Customers' Loyalty, Customers' Patronage, Customers Satisfaction, Marketing, Marketing mix, Organizational performance, Revenue

INTRODUCTION

Rivalry in the markets is becoming firmer as the operational background of business is continuously varying in complexities. A diversity of corporations appear to require that their clienteles are in quest of improved services and worth from opposing trademarks to get

gratification, and extra worth for their money. Hyun (2010) discoursed that the matter of client's support and devotion came to the facade when sellers understand that numerous discontented clienteles don't fundamentally yield to purchase their services and

products and which afterwards affects revenue generated from sales.

In the context of marketing, Customer patronage is the purchase of goods and service from a vendor by a customer or a business. The customer purchases and expects to derive benefits or satisfaction from the goods or services as contemplation for the exchange for money paid. According to Anderson and Sullivan (1993), customer expectations of satisfaction lead to an increase in tendencies to purchasing a particular brand. They reiterated that firms that provide high quality products and services on a habitual basis will have more satisfied customers and these customers will likely patronize the service and products next time. These assertions are supported by Kivela, Inbakaran and Reece (1999) when indicating that comparatively, firms that offer service of superior quality is bound to get their customers satisfied as well as get higher economic returns more than their competitors. Oftentimes managers use customer satisfaction to forecast brand loyalty that ultimately leads to repurchase. On this basis it is expected that customers of restaurants with opt for the sources that meet their quality and value expectations over those that do not; and ignorant will experience customer traffic decline as guests support competing restaurants (Stevens, Knutson and Patton, 1995). Thus, a customer's patronage and loyalty is founded not only on firm's remarkable but may also be influenced by other factors such as restaurant image, personnel quality, food quality, restaurant atmosphere, and products' price, that is pivotal in the delivery process. The effective combination of the marketing mix elements can drive the organization towards their objective and improve their performance in term of short term and long-term performance of the company to improve customer's patronage and loyalty. If customer's patronage is low, there will be decrease in the profit level, low productivity, wastages in resources and other factors that can bring up loss to the company. Customers of fast-food restaurants (FFRs) are diverse in their cultural, economic, and social backgrounds and, in the same manner differ in their desires and expectations. It also means that they have different criteria and factors guiding their choices and decisions for patronage. Restaurants that will thrive in this competitive market must of necessity, understand the nature and characteristics of these desires and expectations and utilize it in providing services to retain existing customers and attract new ones.

LITERATURE REVIEW

This study includes the theoretical framework, the conceptual framework and the empirical reviews. The theoretical framework explains the theories backed up with this study, The conceptual framework elaborates the concepts behind this study, the models associated with

the aims and objectives of the study and the Empirical review explains the artwork of other scholars in this study, their belief, ideologies, values and norms.

Theoretical Framework

The theoretical framework is centered basically on the theory of Satisfaction-Loyalty Relationship, Theory of Attitudinal and Behavioural Loyalty and Theory of Transaction-Specific Satisfaction and Overall Satisfaction.

Theory of Satisfaction-Loyalty Relationship

According to Henning-Thurau and Klee (1997), studies dealing with the relationship between customer satisfaction and loyalty can be classified into three groups. The first comes from service management literature and studies the relationship at an aggregated, company-wide level. These studies consider satisfaction to be an antecedent of customer loyalty, which in turn influences firms' profitability. The second focuses on the individual level and has mainly studied customer retention by customer repurchase intentions. This constitutes an important shortcoming because of the gap between individual intentions and behaviours. This second group perceives loyalty to be influenced by satisfaction, even if the structure of the relationship does not appear to be symmetric and linear. The third group, which is the smallest, has focused on the satisfaction-loyalty link on an individual level with real purchasing data. Henning-Thurau and Klee (1997) found that studies of this group have tended to reveal a weak or insignificant relationship between satisfaction and repurchase behaviour. These views appear complementary, and, according to Henning-Thurau and Klee (1997), it is time for a fourth group of researchers to integrate this dual conceptualisation.

Theory of Attitudinal and Behavioral Loyalty

The first marketing studies perceived customer loyalty in a behavioural way, measuring the concept as behaviour involving the repeat purchase of a particular product or service, evaluated either by the sequence in which it is purchased, as a proportion of purchases, as an act of recommendation, as the scale of the relationship, its scope, or both, or as several of these criteria combined. Since Day (1969) criticised this one-dimensional view as behaviourallycentred and therefore unable to distinguish true loyalty from spurious loyalty, many researchers have recognised the need to add an attitudinal component to the behavioural one. Indeed, as Bandyopadhyay and Martell (2007) found, the existence of such situational

factors as stock being out or unavailable, such individual or intrinsic factors as resistance to change, or such social and cultural factors as social bonding reinforces the need to distinguish customer loyalty from repeat purchase behaviour. These factors also point to a need to add an attitudinal dimension for customer loyalty. This seems to be particularly contextual and therefore relevant in the services area.

Theory of Transaction-Specific Satisfaction and Overall Satisfaction

Johnson (2001) found that two conceptualisations of customer satisfaction had emerged over the previous decade. Before the late 1990s, measurement of satisfaction essentially focused on particular product or service transactions, defined as post-choice evaluative judgments concerning specific purchase decisions. More recently, another conception emerged that is concerned with all of a consumer's previous experiences with a firm, product, or service cumulatively. This perspective considers transaction-specific satisfaction mainly by focusing on consumers' emotional reactions to specific service attributes or service encounters and suggests that firms link the performance of precise service elements or variations of them to specific psychological responses. However, overall satisfaction seems to be a better predictor of customer intentions and behaviours. Thus, according to Johnson (2001), these perspectives seem to be more complementary than competitive, and should therefore be investigated simultaneously, as they do not respond to the same managerial objective-based behaviour.

Conceptual Framework

The conceptual framework reveals the dependent and independent variable in which the dependent variable is customers' patronage and the independent variable is marketing mix

Marketing Mix

The twenty-first century processes of globalization result in a significant change in all business environments. Companies have to change their usual practices. Nowadays, trading companies that seek to meet the needs of customers cannot rely on any previous job application techniques. Customers are becoming choosier; they are not sufficient for traditional marketing solutions. Users are encouraged to exchange a trading sector company, whereas its management has to adapt and to provide an updated marketing mix.

Product

Product is the first element of 4ps and the most important part in the marketing strategies because it will represent the image of the company. The company needs to make sure that the first impression is positives, so the customers see the product and need to plan carefully the product strategies.

Price

Price is the second element of the mix marketing that can be known as the value charged for any product or service. Fixing the product price is a most difficult process for the company because they need to consider a lot of factor like the need of a product, cost involved, consumer's liability to pay, rules and regulation in different countries, government restrictions, prices charged by competitors for the similar products.

Empirical Review

Onigbinde and Odunlami (2015) evaluated the influence of marketing mix on consumer buying decision among beverage consumers in Lagos State, Nigeria. Descriptive survey research design was employed for the study. Descriptive statistics and Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient were used to analyze the data gathered from the respondents. Findings of the study indicated that brand image has a significant influence on consumer buying decision among beverage consumers in Lagos State, Nigeria. Advertising has a significant relationship with consumer buying decision.

Afande and Maina (2015) evaluated the influence of marketing mix elements on sales volume of financial institutions in Kenya using Kenya Post Office Savings Bank as a case study. Descriptive research design was used for the study. This study was carried out in Kenya Post Office Savings Bank headquarters in Nairobi, Kenya. Descriptive statistics, Pearson's Chisquare test, and regression analysis were used to analyze the data gathered from the respondents.

Enitilo, Ajayi, and Famuagun (2017) evaluated the effect of marketing mix on customer patronage of insurance firms in Ado-Ekiti Metropolis, Ekiti State, Nigeria. The study employed survey research design. The respondents comprised of customers of ten selected insurance firms that have business operating in Ado-Ekiti, Ekiti State. Stratified random sampling technique was used for the study. Descriptive statistics was used to analyze the respondents' demography while inferential statistics (multiple regression analysis) was used to test the hypothesis formulated.

Shirisha and Sucharitha (2017) examined the impact of marketing mix on consumers' purchasing decision.

Population of the study comprised of managers, staff, and customers of fast moving consumer goods (FMCG) companies in Jordan. Primary data was collected with the aid of a questionnaire. Descriptive statistics was used to analyze the respondents' demography and responses on each item of the research instrument while multiple regression analysis was used to test the hypotheses formulated.

Grönroos (1984) identified three dimensions of service quality: functional quality, technical quality, and corporate image. Functional quality represents how the service is delivered; that is, it defines the two-way flow that results between the customers and the service providers. Technical quality refers to the outcome of the service act, or what the customer receives in the service encounter. Technical and functional quality, both is preoccupied with psychological and behavioral aspects (Caruana, 2002). For instance, how the service personnel performs their job, what they say and so forth. The model also recognizes that clients have an image about the company (Grönroos, 1984), which has a quality influence in itself and acts as a strainer of customer perceptions (Kang and James, 2004).

Kang and James (2004) contended that a positive and memorable image is valuable for any service firm due to its influence on customer perceptions of service quality. Thereby, perceived service quality is the outcome of the assessment between customers' expectations and perceptions, taking into account the effect of the company image. Bateson and Hoffman (2011) pointed out that "service quality is an attitude formed by a long-term, overall evaluation of performance". They explained that the manner of service delivery, as well as the outcomes, affects the perceptions of customers about the quality.

Kenyon and Sen (2015) have pointed out physical aspects of the service (e.g., equipment, facilities), and the firm's brand image as the factors that has an effect on customer perceptions about quality. The disconfirmation paradigm is the foundation for Parasuraman et al. (1985, 1988) SERVQUAL model, which compares customer expectations and perceptions regarding a particular service or industry. SERVQUAL consists of 22-items divided into five dimensions: reliability, responsiveness, assurance, empathy, and tangibility; several researchers have used and extended the 22-item scale to study service quality in different sectors of the service industry. However, the replication of the model raised many concerns both theoretical and psychometric (Caruana, 2002). First, the conceptualization of customer expectations was questioned (e.g., Cronin and Taylor, 1992). Scholars argued that expectations change over time, and are measured, mostly before receiving the service (Palmer, 2014).

Second, Babakus and Boller (1992), Cronin and Taylor (1992) have found that customer perceptions are an excellent predictor of service quality than the

disconfirmation approach. Third, a number of researchers have reported a different number of dimensions (e.g., Carman, 1990; Cronin and Taylor, 1992). As a result, Cronin and Taylor (1992) have developed a performance-based measure (i.e. SERVPERF) alternative to the SERVQUAL measure. The performance-based model captures customers' perceptions of the service quality offered by a specific service provider (Cronin and Taylor, 1992). Therefore, this paper uses SERVQUAL scale to measure service quality, customer satisfaction, and customer loyalty in retail banking context of Mozambique.

Summary and Gap in the Literature

The literature summarizes the theoretical, empirical and conceptual review of the relationship that exists between marketing mixes and consumers' patronage and loyalty. The theoretical framework pointed out associated theories of the study, the conceptual framework deals with the associated variables that are in the objectives of the study in the previous chapter and the empirical review explains the work of other authors on the study in relation to correlation and regression analysis which will be further used in this study in the data analysis part.

RESEARCH METHODS

Preamble

This chapter presents the research methodology for the study. Specifically, this chapter contains the information about how the researcher collected data for analysis and explanation on the choice of instrument used for data collection. The chapter contains the research design, population of study, sample and sampling procedure, data collection instrument, validation and reliability and statistical tools and analytical procedure.

Research Design

The descriptive research design will be used and the survey method of research will be adopted for this study. This will be adopted due to its distinguished flexibility with respect to method use in gaining in-sight and developing hypothesis. This will enable the research to describe and give full analysis of data collected which resulted into valuable suggestion and recommendation.

Population of Study

The target populations for the study are the customers of five different branches of Domino Pizza in Lagos, which are: Surulere Branch, Along ShopRite, Bode Thomas,

Yaba Branch, Along Harvey Road, Yaba, Lagos, Gbagada Branch, Ilupeju Branch., Apapa Branch.

Sample Size and Sampling Technique

Due to the large population size, random sampling was taken to reduce the volume of data to a manageable proportion. Then Simple Random Sampling will be used to seek the opinions of participants. Taro Yamane formula was used to determine the sample from the population.

Data Collection Instrument

Questionnaire is considered as the main instrument for data collection. Self-administered structured questionnaire will be used to collect data from the customers to measure the level of patronage. To increase the response rate, the questionnaires will be precise and comprehensive. The questionnaire will consist of sections.

Sections A consist of bio-data of the participant, Section B consist of questions related to the research topic.

Method of Data Presentation, Analysis and Interpretation.

The main instruments used in sourcing the required data were structured questionnaire and interviews. They were designed and administered to the purposely selected respondents.

Limitation of the Methodology

For the duration of the paperwork of questionnaire, the researcher had to deal with an engorged amount of participants in following a line of investigation. Since the questions were in random order, some of the customers are seeing the questions for the first time. They were visibly uncomfortable, that will be even in spite of assurances given by researcher that the information required was strictly for research and academic purposes. The COVID 19 restriction was also a limitation due to government policy. Some of them asked for time to make up their minds as to whether to complete the questionnaires.

RESULT

This chapter of this research work presents the respondents ideology on the validated research

questions, analysis of data acquired from the field and the tests of the research hypotheses. A total of Three hundred questionnaires (300), as calculated in chapter 3, were distributed among the customers of Domino Pizza in the five outlets on the mainland in Lagos, of which only one hundred and twenty (120) questionnaires were completed and returned.

Analysis of Demographic Data

This section presents the research respondents demographic data according to their gender, age, marital status, qualification and work experience of the number of respondents in order to help the readers understand the data of the respondents on which the research was administered. From the respondents' frequency counts and percentages of the gender, age distribution, marital status, educational qualification, work experience. The gender distribution of the respondents indicates that 62.5% were male while 37.5% were female this shows that more than half of the population were populated by males.

This study further reveals the age group category of the respondents, 26.7% were below 25 years, respondents between age 36-45 years was 30.0%, also respondents between 46-55 years were 9.2%, respondents within the age of 56-65 years was 5.0% and respondents that are 65 years and above are 6.7%. Hence, majority of the respondents involved were between 25-35 years. The distribution of the respondents' level of education showed that 70.8% of the respondents are BSc holders, 24.2% respondents are MSc holders while 5.0% are PhD holders. This implying a higher proportion of the total respondents had BSc certifications in their academic pursuit.

Marital status of the respondents, 45% respondents are single, 54.2% are married this implies that majority of the respondent are married. The number of service years expended by each respondent on the job of this study showed that; 27.5% had spent 1-5years, 30% had spent 6-10 years, 17.5% had spent 11-15 years and 25% have spent 16years and above. The implication of this is that a higher proportion of the respondents had 6-10years experience on the job.

Analysis of Price Mix

The descriptive analysis indicated that 10.4% of the respondents strongly agreed, 52.8% agreed, 22.6% were undecided, 4.4% disagreed while the remaining 4.7% strongly disagreed that the company sets a low price to increase sales and market share. Furthermore, the analysis showed that 7.5% of the respondents strongly agreed, 40.6% agreed, 41.5% were undecided, 8.5% disagreed while the remaining 1.9% disagreed that the

company sets an initial high price and then slowly lowers the price to make the product available to a wider market. The analysis also indicated that 14.3% of the respondents strongly agreed, 43.8% agreed, 25.7% were undecided, 13.3% disagreed while the remaining 2.9% strongly disagreed which shows that the company sets a price in comparison with competitors. The percentage descriptive analysis moreso indicated that 8.6% of the respondents strongly agreed, 41.9% agreed, 84.3% were undecided, 13.3% disagreed while the remaining 1.9% strongly disagreed which shows that the company price different products within the same product range at different price points. Lastly, the responses indicated that 6.6% of the respondents strongly agreed, 44.3% agreed, 37.7% were undecided, 9.4% disagreed while the remaining 1.9% strongly disagreed which shows that the company bundles a group of products at a reduced price.

Analysis of Place Mix Responses

Analysis of responses to Place Mix of the marketing mix indicated that 5.7% of the respondents strongly agreed, 50.5% agreed, 28.6% were undecided, 11.4% disagreed while the remaining 3.8% strongly disagreed which shows that the company directly distributes its products to consumers. The analysis further indicated that 11.4% of the respondents strongly agreed, 41.9% agreed, 37.1% were undecided, 6.7% disagreed while the remaining 2.9% strongly disagreed which shows that the company indirectly distributes its products to consumers. The descriptive analysis also indicated that 10.5% of the respondents strongly agreed, 48.6% agreed, 34.3% were undecided, 4.8% disagreed while the remaining 1.9% strongly disagreed which shows that the company directly and indirectly distributes its products to consumers. The analysis further indicated that 12.4% of the respondents strongly agreed, 61.1% agreed, 31.9% were undecided, 3.8% disagreed while the remaining 1.0% strongly disagreed which shows that the company distributes its products to consumers via intermediaries.

Analysis of Product Mix of Respondents

Product Mix analysis of respondents wereas follow; 10.9% of the respondents strongly agreed, 35.6% agreed, 33.7% were undecided, 16.8% disagreed while the remaining 3.0% strongly disagreed which shows that the company products are easy to consume for customers. The analysis further indicated that 13.9% of the respondents strongly agreed, 51.5% agreed, 27.7% were undecided, 5.0% disagreed while the remaining 2.0% strongly disagreed which shows that the company provide a better consumer experience. The respondents analysis further indicated that 10.0% of the respondents strongly agreed, 48.0% agreed, 32.0% were undecided,

9.0% disagreed while the remaining 1.0% strongly disagreed which shows that the company have a durable and attractive visual design. The analysis further indicated that 20.0% of the respondents strongly agreed, 49.0% agreed, 26.0% were undecided, 4.0% disagreed while the remaining 1.0% strongly disagreed which shows that the company minimize the product cost to better profit margins. The descriptive analysis further indicated that 23% of the respondents strongly agreed, 53.0% agreed, 19.0% were undecided, 4.0% disagreed while the remaining 1.0% strongly disagreed which shows that the company provides a solution to the consumer's problems, needs and wants.

Analysis of Promotion Mix Respondents

Analysis of Promotion Mix Respondents indicated that 20.8% of the respondents strongly agreed, 49.5% agreed, 23.8% were undecided, while the remaining 5.9% disagreed that the company use advertising as a vital tool for increasing brand awareness. Also, the analysis indicated that 12.1% of the respondents strongly agreed, 35.4% agreed, 37.4% were undecided, 12.1% disagreed while the remaining 3.0% strongly disagreed that the company use personal selling as a vital tool for increasing brand awareness. This discussion of the analysis furthermore indicated that 19% of the respondents strongly agreed, 37.0% agreed, 34.0% were undecided, 7.0% disagreed while the remaining 3.0% strongly disagreed that the Company use public relations as a vital tool for increasing brand awareness. This result further indicated that 24.8% of the respondents strongly agreed, 46.5% agreed, 21.8% were undecided, 5.0% disagreed while the remaining 2.0% strongly disagreed that the company use direct marketing as a vital tool for increasing brand awareness. And lastly, the descriptive analysis indicated that 21.8% of the respondents strongly agreed, 50.5% agreed, 19.8% were undecided, 5.9% disagreed while the remaining 2.0% strongly disagreed that the company use direct selling as a vital tool for increasing brand awareness.

Analysis of Customers Purchases Responses

Analysis of Customers Purchases Responses indicated that 20.6% of the respondents strongly agreed, 47.1% agreed, 21.6% were undecided, 21.6% disagreed while the remaining 1.0% strongly disagreed that assortments are critical determinants of customers purchases. The result further indicated that 10.0% of the respondents strongly agreed, 48.0% agreed, 32.0% were undecided, 9.0% disagreed while the remaining 1.0% strongly disagreed which shows that fast checkouts are critical determinants of customers purchases. The analysis further indicated that 6.6% of the respondents strongly

Table 1. Mean, Standard Deviation and Zero Order correlation Matrices showing the Relationship among the Study Variables

Variables	Mean	SD	1	2	3	4	5
CUSPTG	16.50	2.852	1				
PRC	13.64	2.740	-.213*	1			
PLC	13.49	2.477	.011	.401**	1		
PDT	14.36	2.728	.227*	.024	.128	1	
PMTN	13.74	3.208	.011	.075	.064	.182*	1

*Correlation is significant at $p < 0.05$ (1- tailed)

**Correlation is significant at $p < 0.01$ (2- tailed)

Key- CUSPTG: customer patronage; PRC: price; PLC: place; PDT: product; PMTN: promotion

Source: field survey correlation analysis from SPSS, 2022

agreed, 44.3% agreed, 37.7% were undecided, 9.4% disagreed while the remaining 1.9% strongly disagreed which shows that location is a critical determinant of customers purchases. The table further indicated that 8.6% of the respondents strongly agreed, 41.9% agreed, 84.3% were undecided, 13.3% disagreed while the remaining 1.9% strongly disagreed which shows that pleasant shopping environment are critical determinants of customers purchase. And lastly, 7.5% of the respondents strongly agreed, 40.6% agreed, 41.5% were undecided, 8.5% disagreed while the remaining 1.9% strongly disagreed that friendly courteous service are critical determinants of customers purchase. Table 1

Hypothesis one states that pricing has an effect on the customers' patronage. This hypothesis was tested using the Pearson correlation analysis on SPSS version 20. The result indicated that there is a significant negative relationship between pricing and customers patronage ($r = -0.213$; $p < 0.01$). This implies that as prices of the product goes up, it will affect customers' patronage negatively that is, customers won't have that urge of patronage to the company. Therefore, hypothesis one is rejected.

Hypothesis two states that place has an effect on the customers' patronage. This hypothesis was tested using the Pearson correlation analysis on SPSS version 20. The result indicated that there is a significant positive relationship between place and customers' patronage ($r = 0.401$; $p < 0.01$). It implies that it is important for the company to have a good understanding about the positioning or place of the business because it has influence on the successful of business in the long term; The product that should be made ready for the customer to found it at a suitable place where they can handily make deal. Therefore, hypothesis two is accepted.

Hypothesis Three states that promotion has an effect on customers' patronage. This hypothesis was tested using the Pearson correlation analysis on SPSS version 20. The result indicated that there is a significant positive relationship between promotion and customers' patronage ($r = 0.182$; $p < 0.01$). It implies that promotion strategy helps to increase consumer awareness in terms of their products, leads to higher sales and helps to build

brand loyalty as it involves the use of various methods such as direct marketing, sales promotion, advertising and public relations. Therefore, hypothesis three is accepted.

Hypothesis Four states that product has an effect on the customers' patronage. This hypothesis was tested using the Pearson correlation analysis on SPSS version 20. The result indicated that there is a significant positive relationship between product and customers' patronage ($r = 0.128$; $p < 0.01$). This implies that, by the right and effective product strategies, the organization can attract the huge number of customers to buy their product as well as to increase their sales and organization performance. Therefore, hypothesis four is accepted.

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION

Preamble

This chapter centers on the discussion of key findings of the study, summary of these findings, the conclusion of the study as well as the implication of the study. It also entails the recommendations made and suggestions for further research are included.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The study projected and verified an aggregate of four hypotheses. The researcher also made some other findings. The study showed that there is a negative significant relationship between price and customers' patronage (H1) which implies that as prices of the product goes up, it will affect customers' patronage negatively that is, customers won't have that urge of patronage to the company. The study further revealed that there is a positive significant relationship between place and customers' patronage which implies that it is important for the company to have a good understanding about the positioning or place of the business because it has influence on the successful of business in the long term.

Furthermore, the study revealed that there is a positive significant relationship between promotion and customers' patronage (H3). The implication is that promotion strategy helps to increase consumer awareness in terms of their products, leads to higher sales and helps to build brand loyalty as it involves the use of various methods such as direct marketing, sales promotion, advertising and public relations.

Finally, the research showed that there is a positive relationship between product and customers' patronage (H4). This implies that, by the right and effective product strategies, the organization can attract the huge number of customers to buy their product as well as to increase their sales and organization performance.

From the above, it can be deduced that most hypothesis were accepted. Although, the extent to which they affect the customers' patronage varies. So, marketing mix has the highest tendency to affect customers' patronage in the correlation analysis.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The main goal of this study was to examine the effects of marketing mixes (Price, Place, Promotion and Product) on the customers' patronage in Domino Pizza. From the correlation analysis, it is observed that there is a positive significant relationship between marketing mixes (Price, Place, Promotion and Product) on customers' patronage in the organization. Therefore, the findings of this study have made it possible to reach the conclusion that marketing mix has significantly positive effects on customers' patronage in Domino Pizza

The following recommendations were made based on the findings and conclusions:

1. New techniques and methods in connection with marketing mix should be adopted to ensure continued customers' patronage and loyalty to Domino Pizza.
2. Favourable pricing should be employed in Domino Pizza and channeled to boosting customers' patronage and loyalty.
3. The customers should be given high and friendly treatments in the organization to ensure more patronages.

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